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Investigating the Factors on Tourist Revisit Intentions and Destination Recommendations in Ada, Ghana

Abstract

This study examines the factors influencing tourists' decision to revisit and recommend the emerging Ada tourist destination in Ghana. Analyzing data from 522 tourists using Factorial Analysis and Mean scores in IBM SPSS, this study identified five destination attribute factors: climate and natural attractions, destination image, accessibility and infrastructure, entertainment and comfort, and hospitality and cultural appeal as antecedents to tourists' intentions to revisit and recommend the incipient Ada destination. This study also highlighted the perceived value and tourist satisfaction with accommodation, food services, transportation, and attraction fees as crucial influencers. Dissatisfaction with the road network and transportation services has emerged as a notable challenge that could impact tourists' revisit intentions and recommendations for the Ada destination. This study offers valuable insights for destination managers, urging strategic interventions to strengthen Ada's appeal, improve accessibility, and enhance overall tourist experiences, intentions, and recommendations.

Keywords: *Emerging Destinations, Revisit Intentions, Destination Recommendation, Destination Competitiveness, Tourism Management*

Jel Classifications: L83, Z32, Z39

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1. Introduction

Tourism remains a vital sector globally, and because of its contemporary competitiveness, destinations are vying for sustained visitor loyalty through positive recommendations and

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repeat visits. Wang and Li (2019) and Yoon and Usyal (2005) stated that repeat visits and destination recommendations among tourists remain the most cost-effective way to determine customer loyalty and develop and market tourism destinations. In this context, understanding the factors that shape tourists' decisions to revisit and recommend a destination to others is critical for destinations, especially emerging ones (Osei, 2022). Consequently, destination recommendations and tourists' revisit intentions have become a focal point of scholarly inquiry to understand tourist destination performance, prospects, and sustainability. Nevertheless, while some studies explored this phenomenon in established tourist destinations (Chi & Qu, 2008; Wang & Li 2019;; Kim et al., 2005; Oliver, 1999), there are notable gaps in the literature concerning emerging tourism destinations. In addition, emerging destinations are usually characterized by limited international exposure and burgeoning tourism infrastructure, thus offering an intriguing context for research exploration towards proper development from the onset (Khan et al., 2020).

Moreover, emerging destinations face unique challenges and opportunities to establish themselves as an attractive destination where tourists can have positive visitor experiences (Khan et al., 2020). Thus, knowing the performance of each destination component and attribute (natural attractions, water resources, infrastructure, services, sociocultural elements, technology, communication, etc.) in terms of satisfaction, the perceived value attached to the experiences, and the destination image formed relative to tourists' likelihood of recommending and revisiting is central (Aliman et al., 2016), especially for the desired and sustainable development and growth of incipient destinations (Zhang et al., 2017).

Furthermore, regarding destination competitiveness and marketing, tourists' revisit intentions and recommendations are grounded partly or wholly in the destination's performance in terms of their experiences and satisfaction with the destination's elements and attributes (Kim et al., 2005). With the potential to become fully fledged tourism destinations, knowledge and understanding of the factors/performances of destination attributes that can positively or negatively impact tourists' revisit intentions and recommendations of emerging destinations are necessary. This is because they can aid in driving proper development, sustainable management, and responsible marketing of emerging destinations among stakeholders (Kim et al., 2005; Wang & Li, 2019; Som et al., 2012).

Therefore, this study was conducted to comprehensively explore the factors influencing tourists' revisit intentions and destination recommendations for Ghana's emerging Ada tourist destination. By doing so, this study endeavored to fill the research gap regarding revisiting intentions and destination recommendations within emerging tourist destinations, offering practical insights for destination managers, industry operators, policymakers, and marketers seeking to enhance visitors' experiences, position their destinations favorably in the competitive global tourism landscape, and foster sustainable tourism destination development.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Tourists Revisit Intentions and Recommendations

Revisit and destination recommendations are the most decisive parameters of tourist destination loyalty (Zhang et al., 2014). Repeat visits and destination recommendations among tourists remain the cheapest/most cost-effective way to market and develop emerging destinations sustainably (Wang and Li, 2019). Revisit intentions and recommendations among tourists play a pivotal role in sustainable tourism development and effective management of destinations (Lee & Hsu, 2013; Zhang & Huang, 2021). This concept denotes the likelihood or intention of tourists/visitors to return to specific destinations for subsequent visits and to recommend them to others. Tourists' revisits and recommendations of destinations are pivotal in shaping the tourism industry in destinations, influencing potential travellers' choices, and contributing to the long-term sustainability of destinations (Aliman et al., 2016). The existing body of literature reveals a nuanced set of factors that impact tourists' decisions to advocate for and revisit a particular destination. The tourist Destination Loyalty Model (TDLM),

proposed by Kim et al. (2005), shows that satisfaction, destination image, and perceived value are key contributing factors to tourists' intentions to revisit and recommend a destination, while satisfaction with destination elements and attributes provides the fundamental tourism experiential determinants (Oliver, 1999). Studies such as Kim and Richardson (2003) and Lee and Hsu (2013) further underscore the positive association between tourist satisfaction and the inclination to recommend and revisit a destination. Baloglu and McCleary (1999) also reported that a positive destination image significantly determines the likelihood of tourists revisiting and recommending a destination. Moreover, hospitality and social-cultural factors have also been identified as playing a substantial role in tourist destination revisits and recommendations (Wang & Li, 2019). This includes positive interactions with locals, peer endorsements, and a sense of community.

2.2 Factors that Influence Destination Recommendation and Revisit Intention

Myriad factors have been identified as influencing tourists' decisions regarding revisiting and recommending destinations (Karakan, 2023). According to the literature, numerous factors encompassing destination attributes, quality, destination attachment, and personal involvement can influence tourism customers' revisit intentions and recommendations about a destination (Kyriakaki et al., 2015; Som et al., 2012). Other contributing elements include tourists' expectations, perceived quality, and perceived value (Aliman et al., 2016; Yoon & Uysal, 2005), as well as prior tourist experiences (Kaplanidou & Vogt, 2007), tourist satisfaction (Aliman et al., 2016; Prayag & Ryan, 2012), and destination image (Chiu et al., 2016; Ramseook-Munhurrin, et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2014).

Furthermore, factors such as the quality of tourist services, quality of destination elements/attributes (Aliman et al., 2016; Serrato et al., 2010), nationality of tourists (Mechinda et al., 2009), the distance between tourists' residences and the destination (McKercher & Denizci, 2011), and stage of tourist development at a destination (Kozak, 2001) have been explored. Despite this array, achieving nostalgic tourism experiences, satisfaction, and benefits linked to a destination increases the likelihood of revisit (Zhang et al. 2017; Barnes et al., 2016). The role of local cultures is pivotal in shaping these experiences (Kim et al., 2010), concurrently influencing the development of positive word-of-mouth (WOM) recommendations. Among these various factors, three primary determinants of tourist revisit and destination recommendations consistently emerge in the literature: destination image, satisfaction, and perceived value based on destination attributes.

2.2.1 Destination Satisfaction

Tourist satisfaction is the defining determinant of destination success, influencing visitors' decisions to recommend and revisit a destination. Scholars such as Chen et al. (2020) argue that satisfaction stems from various factors, including attraction and infrastructure, service quality, cultural experiences, and destination attributes. Positive experiences lead to satisfaction and favorable recommendations (Kim et al., 2021) and impact destination image as well (Wang & Li, 2019). Revisit intentions, as emphasized by Oliver (2014), are often a consequence of high satisfaction levels with the various elements and attributes of the destination. Zhang and Huang, (2021) underscore the reciprocity between satisfaction, recommendations, and revisits. For destination managers and leaders in emerging destinations, understanding the performance of their destination through these interconnected dynamics is crucial for the effective development, improvement, management, and marketing of their destinations (Sánchez-Rebull et al., 2018).

Tourists are often satisfied with destinations that offer attractions and well-developed and well-maintained infrastructure, including natural and man-made beaches, efficient transportation, amenities, and communication infrastructure (Buhalis & Michopoulou, 2011; Wang & Xu, 2006). Recent studies have also emphasized the growing significance of technology and smart infrastructure in enhancing tourist experiences and impacting revisit

intentions (Sigala, 2017). On the other hand, satisfaction with accommodation, service delivery, and staff performance are critical factors influencing tourists' decisions to recommend a destination and return. Research shows that favorable experiences with destination accommodations, restaurants, prices, and high-quality services significantly contribute to positive word-of-mouth and repeat visitation (Gursoy et al., 2016). In the hotel context, Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry's (1988) SERVQUAL model, which focuses on service quality dimensions, has been widely applied to understand the intricacies of customer perceptions. Recent studies by Wang and Li (2019) delve into the impact of hotel attributes, such as cleanliness, staff responsiveness, and amenities, on tourist satisfaction and subsequent destination recommendations. Furthermore, Chen and Tsai (2020) highlight the evolving role of online reviews in shaping destination choices, emphasizing the influence of the internet and peer-generated content on tourists' decision-making processes.

Moreover, satisfaction with the socio-cultural aspects of a destination, including local traditions, customs/festivities, and community engagement, significantly impacts tourist perceptions (Kim & Jogaratnam, 2019). Tourist perceptions and satisfaction levels are notably shaped by pivotal social and cultural factors (Kim, 2018). Destination recommendations are significantly influenced by positive interactions with local communities, cultural authenticity, and engaging social experiences (Stepchenkova & Li, 2012). Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory (1980) offers a valuable framework for comprehending how cultural values impact travel decisions. In addition, tourists' cultural intelligence plays a vital role in contributing to positive destination evaluations and fostering intentions to revisit (Wang et al., 2021). Understanding the performance of socio-cultural elements in tourist satisfaction and tourist behavioral outcomes is essential for destination managers and marketers aiming to grow and enhance their destination. Thus, their appeals to encourage repeat visitation and recommendations are fundamental. Tourism industry now heavily relies on the widespread availability of the internet and network connectivity, influencing factors that impact destination recommendations and tourists' decisions to revisit. Visitors' capacity to share real-time experiences through online platforms significantly affects their overall satisfaction and engagement with a destination (Li et al., 2018). Positive online interactions play a crucial role in encouraging tourists to recommend a destination, contributing to the formation of a favorable destination image (Wang & Hsu, 2010). Moreover, the seamless connectivity experience directly influences tourists' choices to revisit, fostering loyalty and a sense of community through immediate experience sharing (Buhalis & Foerste, 2015). Despite these advantages, challenges such as digital divides and connectivity disparities can hinder the effectiveness of these interactions (Xiang et al., 2017).

2.2.2 Destination Image

Destination image encompasses both cognitive and affective dimensions, and holds substantial sway over tourists' decisions to revisit, as demonstrated by studies such as those by Fakeye and Crompton (1991) and Baloglu and McCleary (1999). A positive destination image not only enhances its overall allure but also fosters a sense of loyalty among tourists (Beerli & Martin, 2004). Balancing cognitive and affective aspects, tourists often form their image through word-of-mouth, marketing communication, and personal experiences (Beerli & Martin, 2004). Destination image is dynamic and evolves because of evolving marketing strategies, socio-cultural changes, and visitor experiences (Pike, 2002). Positive destination image significantly contributes to tourist satisfaction and loyalty, impacting destination competitiveness (Chen & Tsai, 2007). Moreover, the impact of information sources on tourists' decisions to revisit cannot be overstated. Online reviews and recommendations, as highlighted by Litvin et al. (2008), exert significant influence, shaping destination choices and impacting revisit intentions. Social media platforms, including TripAdvisor and Instagram, contribute to the dissemination of destination information, shaping tourists' expectations and influencing their inclination to return, as noted by Xiang et al. (2017).

2.2.3 Perceived Value

Perceived value is a multidimensional construct that encompasses both tangible and intangible elements and various factors such as price fairness, service quality, and overall satisfaction. It emerges as a key determinant shaping tourists' attitudes and behaviours. Scholars, including Bigne et al. (2009), highlight the role of perceived value in enhancing visitor satisfaction and the likelihood of recommending a destination. Furthermore, the works of Kim et al. (2015), Kim et al. (2013), and Chen and Tsai (2007) underscore the link between perceived value and tourists' intention to revisit. These studies indicate that tourists are more likely to recommend a destination and express intentions to revisit when they perceive that the value received (experiences and satisfaction) exceed the cost of travelling to the destination. Knowing whether or not tourists had value for money at a given destination is evident in their indication of satisfaction, perception of a favorable value proposition, and being more likely to endorse and revisit a destination (Karakan, 2023).

Overall, this review suggests that revisit and destination recommendations among tourists are determined by multidimensional elements which are not limited to the level of satisfaction, experience or created destination image, and perceived value accrued (based on cost-benefit analysis) at the destinations (Kim et al., 2015). These elements extend to many other variables and parameters because destinations differ in many contexts, content, and appeal. In most emerging destinations, the performances of their individual and collective attributes and tourism offerings, in terms of satisfaction values and experiences, relative to tourist expectations remain majorly unknown. However, this is vital to provide data, basis, and guidance for suitable development and effective management of most tourism destinations, especially emergent ones, to deliver the desired experience to tourists, which in turn helps to impact repeat visitation, recommendation, and sustainability of the destination (Kim, et al., 2021; Zhang & Huang, 2021).

3. Research Methods

3.1 Study Area

The Ada tourism region is one of the premier emerging destinations situated along the eastern coastal region of Ghana. This destination (Ada East District) is located within latitudes of 5°45' and 6°00' (North) and longitudes of 0°20' to 0°35' (East). Notably, Ada has a unique feature: the Ada Estuary, which is the only one of its kind in Ghana. This natural wonder, complemented by the increasing development of tourism facilities, a flourishing island tourism scene, pristine beaches, diverse water sports opportunities, and the lively cultural celebration of the Asafotufiami Festival, contributes to its distinct appeal. Additionally, the region holds promise for ecotourism ventures (Odikro, 2014). Recent data from the Ghana Statistical Service in 2021 indicate that Ada is home to approximately 76,000 permanent residents and its reputation as an enticing and viable tourist hub is steadily growing. The current surge in tourist and visitor numbers to the emerging Ada tourism region emphasizes the need for research to assess tourists' willingness to revisit and recommend this destination among other emerging destinations in the sub-region. Such insights derived from encounters, experiences, and satisfaction with various destination attributes will be instrumental in guiding a destination's proper development into a fully-fledged and thriving tourism hub.

3.2 Research Population and Sample

The population of this research involves tourists who visited the Ada tourist region between 3rd July 2022 and 16th November 2022 and who have spent at least one night at the Ada tourist region (beaches and beach facilities, in-land and riverside hotels and chalets, island facilities, attractions sites, participants in the Asafotufiami festival). The research sampled 522 tourists as respondents. This involves 269 international and 253 domestic tourists to the Ada tourist region. For a quantitative study such as this, a minimum of 100 participants is

sufficient and appropriate for statistical estimations (Brida & Scuderi, 2013; Hair et al., 2013), hence, a sample of 522 respondents collected for this study was considered adequate.

3.3 Data Collection and Measures

In consonance with the quantitative methodology, the study used the survey method using a self-administered questionnaire, with items from the literature review, particularly, those by Zhang et al. (2017), Aliman et al., (2016), Barnes et al. (2016), Kyriakaki et al. (2015), Ramseook-Munhurrun et al. (2015), Zhang et al. (2014), Chen & Phou (2013), Som et al. (2012), Kim et al. (2005), Praya & Rayan (2012), and Serrato et al. (2010). The questionnaire was composed of three parts: Part 1 contained 35 scale items (composed of destination attributes and perceived value); Part 2 contained 24 scale items (destination overall satisfaction and revisit intention and recommendation); and the final part, Part 3, contained five questions on socio-demographic variables. Scales were used and Part 1 and Part 2 were measured through 59 items on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 to 5, as displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: Measurement Scale and Interpretation.

Survey responses	<i>Destination attributes, Perceive Value and Revisit Intention and Recommendation</i>	<i>Satisfaction</i>	Scale
Strongly Agree	Very much	Very Satisfying	4.50 – 5.00
Agree	Much	Satisfying	3.50 – 4.49
Indifferent	Uncertain	Uncertain	2.50 -3.49
Disagree	Not Much	Not Satisfying	1.50 -2.49
Strongly Disagree	Not Much at all	Not at all Satisfying	1.00 -1.49

Source: Authors

This study employed a convenience sampling method to collect the data. Given that there are no data on beach visitors or tourists, and that they are typically mobile populations, employing a probability sampling procedure or tracking them becomes challenging. Consequently, this study synchronizes with many others such as Su et al., (2021), Khairi and Darmawan (2021), Nguyen (2020), and Miao (2015), and employed the convenience sampling technique to address the logistical challenges associated with studying this mobile research population.

3.4 Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using IBM SPSS (version 25). Initially, the study characterized respondents based on their socio-demographic features. Subsequently, a factor analysis employing the principal component method with varimax rotation was conducted to reveal the fundamental factors within the 28 destination attributes and 7 perceived value items. Lastly, descriptive statistics were employed to calculate the mean scores for the 14 overall items assessing tourists' satisfaction with the destination. Additionally, the mean scores for a total of 10 items related to tourists' revisit intentions and destination recommendations for the emerging destination in Ghana were computed.

4. Results

4.1 Profile of Sample

The results of the study in Table 2 indicate that, in terms of gender, most respondents were male (52.4%), while females constituted 47.6%. Regarding age, a significant portion (36.9%)

fell within the 21-30 age range, followed by individuals aged 31-40 (25.7%), and those aged 41 and above (21.5%). Respondents aged 20 years or below made up 15.9% of the sample. Educational levels varied, with a notable percentage having tertiary education (49.6%), followed by post-graduate (26.5%), and high school (23.9%). Marital status distribution indicated that a significant proportion of respondents were single (46.7%), followed by married individuals (40.0%), and those who were divorced (15.3%). In terms of nationality, the study included both domestic (51.5%) and international participants (49.5%). These results reveal diverse demographic factors that provide a nuanced and broad basis for acknowledging, understanding, and considering the essence of the study results regarding factors influencing tourists' revisit intentions and destination recommendations in the emerging Ada destination of Ghana. Moreover, recognizing the distribution of participants across demographic categories enhances the generalizability and applicability of the study's conclusions.

Table 2: Profile of the Sample.

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	274	52.4
Female	248	47.6
Age		
≤20	83	15.9
21- 30	192	36.9
31 - 40	123	25.7
41≥	124	21.5
Educational level		
High school	125	23.9
Tertiary	259	49.6
Post-graduate	138	26.5
Marital status		
Single	244	46.7
Married	209	40.0
Divorced	69	15.3
Nationality		
Domestic	269	51.5
International	253	49.5

Source: Authors

4.2 Factorial Analysis and Means

To determine the fundamental dimensions influencing tourists' intentions to revisit and recommend a destination, we conducted a principal component factor analysis to categorize destination attribute items based on common characteristics. Barlett's test of sphericity

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yielded statistically significant results ($X^2 = 7896.16$; $p = 0.001$) and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin value of .896 surpassed the recommended threshold of 0.6 (Hair et al., 1995). To assess the reliability and internal consistency, a reliability analysis (overall Cronbach's alpha = 0.816) was performed, and variables with factor loadings of 0.40 and above (Stevens, 1992) were considered and used for further interpretation of the factors. The results, presented in Table 3, indicate that the factor analysis of 28 destination attributes led to the identification of five distinct factor groupings, collectively explaining 61.73% of the variance. These factor groupings encompassed "climate and natural attraction," "destination image," "accessibility and infrastructure suitability," "entertainment and comfort," and "hospitality and cultural appeal". Notably, "climate and natural attraction" emerged as the most influential destination attribute for both repeat visitation and destination recommendation among tourists, accounting for 22.81% of the variance with an eigenvalue of 12.23.

Table 3: Factors Loads and Means of the Destination Attributes.

Latent constructs	Factor Loading	Eigen-value	Variance Explained	Cronbach alpha	Mean
<i>Climate and Natural Attraction</i>		12.23	22.81	0.833	4.01
Offers fresh water for tourism and cruising.	0.891				4.13
This destination offers pleasant weather and climate for tourism.	0.895				4.16
Has diverse attractive natural resources/areas for tourists' delight	0.872				3.89
Provides natural Islands for unique experiences	0.892				3.99
It offers clean and attractive beaches to behold.	0.831				3.86
<i>Destination Image</i>		10.21	15.78	0.892	3.76
I consider the Ada region as having unique and attractive islands for tourism.	0.821				3.89
The beaches in the Ada region offer serenity and an enjoyable atmosphere.	0.723				4.04
I perceive the Ada region as providing special opportunities for water travel and cruise activities.	0.712				3.67
Tourists have a unique opportunity to witness the meeting of the Atlantic Ocean and the mighty Volta River at Ada.	0.716				4.12
Ada Tourism has proactive staff at tourist attractions and facilities in the region.	0.633				3.12
<i>Accessibility and Infrastructure Suitability</i>		7.41	12.12	0.783	3.45
The Ada destination (attractions, locations of interest, facilities) is easily accessible.	0.671				2.43
Offers an exclusive natural environment for tourism activities.	0.831				3.67
It has modern facilities that meet tourists' needs.	0.769				3.89
It provides a stable internet connection for tourists to share their experiences.	0.899				4.54
Ensures enough connectivity for tourists to	0.893				4.53

communicate with friends and family back home.					
The Ada region has a good transportation system to easily connect tourists to the destination.	0.452				2.53
Good transport to connect various attractions and facilities where tourists are lodged.	0.521				2.56
<i>Entertainment and Comfort</i>		3.31	6.13	0.784	3.26
Offers opportunities for entertainment.	0.782				3.98
The destination is secure and safe enough for tourists to easily and freely enjoy their travel.	0.721				3.97
The destination has good and knowledgeable staff at its facilities and attractions	0.431				3.12
The cleanliness of the destination	0.642				3.34
Availability of ATM machines, forex, and other systems for tourists to withdraw/exchange money at ease	0.432				1.89
<i>Hospitality and Cultural Appeal</i>		2.79	4.89	0.791	3.66
Local people in Ada are friendly towards tourists.	0.789				3.85
The Ada region offers a rich diversity of enjoyable local foods.	0.769				3.78
Tourism in Ada includes unique cultural displays and experiences.	0.831				3.98
English is widely spoken among the local population in Ada.	0.732				3.12
I feel that tourism in Ada offers good value for money.	0.647				3.56
<i>Total Variance explained = 61.73%</i>				0.816	
KMO = 0.896;		Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (X2) = 7896.16;		p= 0.001	

Scale: Strongly Disagree = 0-1.49, Disagree = 1.5-2.49, neutral = 2.5-3.49, Agree= 3.5-4.49, Strongly Agree = 4.5-5.0. Source: Authors

The analysis followed the same procedure to examine the 7 perceived destination value (value for money) items. This process aimed to uncover the underlying dimensions associated with both revisit intentions and destination recommendations, based on the perceived values experienced at the Ada tourist destination. Two factors emerged, each with eigenvalues surpassing one. The composite reliability test affirmed a reliability coefficient of 0.811 for the perceived destination value factors. As presented in Table 4, the factor analysis of the seven perceived destination value items revealed two distinct factor groupings, collectively explaining 62.70% of the variance. These factor groupings are categorized as "value for individual travel experience" and "value for overall travel experience." Markedly, "perceived value for individual travel experience" emerged as the most influential factor impacting the revisit intentions and destination recommendations of tourists. This factor accounted for 44.19% of the variance, with an eigenvalue of 6.69.

Table 4: Factorial Loads and Means of the Destination’s Perceived Value

Perceived Value constructs	Factor Loading	Eigen-value	Variance explained	Cronbach alpha	Mean
<i>Value of Individual Attributes</i>		6.69	44.19	0.829	2.84
The cost of entertainment in the Ada region is reasonable and represents good value for	0.812				4.12

money.

The cost of accommodation in the Ada region is justifiable considering the quality and amenities provided.	0.678				2.62
I find the cost of food services in the Ada region to be reasonable in relation to the quality and variety offered.	0.562				3.03
The transportation costs within the Ada region are reasonable, considering the convenience and accessibility provided.	0.621				2.32
The fees associated with attractions and recreational activities in the Ada region are fair and reflect the value of the experiences offered	0.612				2.12
<i>Value in Overall Attributes</i>		3.57	18.51	0.793	3.71
I believe the Ada region provides a good overall value for the cost of my travel experience.	0.761				3.76
Considering the overall costs incurred during my stay in the Ada region, I feel satisfied with the value for money.	0.541				3.65
<i>Total Variance explained = 62.7%</i>				0.811	
KMO = 0.793;		Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity (X2) = 2411.04;		p= 0.000	

Scale: Strongly Disagree = 0-1.49, Disagree = 1.5-2.49, neutral = 2.5-3.49, Agree= 3.5-4.49, Strongly Agree = 4.5-5.0. Source: Authors

Furthermore, a descriptive statistical analysis was employed to determine the key dimensions influencing tourists’ satisfaction with the destination. As depicted in Table 5, the statement "The beaches here" secured the highest mean (4.21), closely followed by "The internet and connectivity in the Ada tourism region" (mean = 4.18), "The safety and security level within the destination" (mean = 4.18), "The tourism at islands here" (mean = 4.03), and "The entertainment/nightlife" (mean = 4.01). These results underscore the critical importance of beach quality, connectivity, safety, island tourism, and entertainment in shaping tourists’ overall satisfaction with the destination. This suggests that participants in the study are likely to consider these five factors when deciding to revisit or recommend the destination to family and friends in the future. The findings also underscore the relationship between tourists’ satisfaction and their intention to revisit or recommend the destination, aligning with established literature (Kim et al., 2020; Zhang & Huang 2021). Particularly, in the Ada region, tourists also emphasize the importance of satisfaction with overall cleanliness (mean score of 3.89) and traditional events (mean = 3.82) in shaping their intent for repeat visits and recommendations. Despite these positive aspects, the study identifies the road network (mean = 2.49) and transportation system and services (mean = 2.41) as significant challenges that require attention to enhance the destination’s appeal. These signal areas require immediate attention. Improving road and transport networks is imperative for ensuring seamless accessibility, and addressing key issues that directly impact the satisfaction and, subsequently, the loyalty of tourists to the Ada region.

Table 5: Overall Satisfaction with the Destination

Statements	Mean	Std. D
How satisfied are you with:		
The tourism at the islands here	4.03	0.72
The beaches here	4.21	0.06
The historical monuments/museums	2.22	1.41
The traditional events at the destination	3.82	1.03
The food (including the local food of the people)	3.43	1.01
The local craft or products	3.21	0.98
The attractions at the destination	3.63	0.98
The transportation system and services	2.41	1.21
The entertainment/nightlife	4.01	0.89
The safety and security level within the destination	4.18	0.71
The road networks in the destination	2.49	1.21
The overall cleanliness of the destination area	3.89	1.01
The internet and connectivity in the Ada tourism region	4.18	0.94
Hospitality and services	3.78	0.99

Scale: Not at all satisfied = 1.0-1.49, Not satisfied = 1.5-2.49, indifferent= 2.5-3.49, Satisfied= 3.5-4.49, Very satisfied = 4.5-5.0. Source: Authors

Likewise, the findings in Table 6, highlighted through a comprehensive statistical analysis, showed a strong inclination among respondents to extend their stay and bring more companions to the Ada tourist region. The statement "I am willing to bring more friends and family when next I visit Ada for tourism" received the highest mean value (4.05), and "Compared to my previous destination, I stayed/will prefer to stay for a longer period here in Ada" closely following (mean = 4.03), suggesting a positive outlook for the region's economic impact through extended tourist stays. Efforts to further encourage and support prolonged visits and stays could enhance the local economy and tourism sustainability.

Table 6: Tourists Revisit Intentions and Destination Recommendation

Statements	Mean	Std. D
I am willing to return to the Ada region for tourism in the future.	3.82	0.99
I am willing to recommend the Ada region as a good holiday/tourist destination for families and friends.	3.98	1.02
I have a delightful/positive image of the Ada region as a growing tourism destination.	3.91	0.98
I would visit new destinations other than those in the Ada region.	3.02	1.78
I feel loyal to Ada as a destination of choice	3.32	1.09

Compared to other destinations I have visited; I spent less money in the Ada region.	2.64	1.89
Compared to my previous destination, I stayed/will prefer to stay for a longer period here in Ada.	4.03	0.72
I am willing to bring more friends and family when next I visit Ada for tourism.	4.05	0.70
I would recommend the Ada region to others based on the perceived value and satisfaction I experienced.	3.84	0.98
The value for money I received in the Ada region makes me inclined to revisit in the future.	3.22	1.01

Scale: Strongly Disagree = 0-1.49, Disagree = 1.5-2.49, neutral = 2.5-3.49, Agree= 3.5-4.49, Strongly Agree = 4.5-5.0. Source: Authors

Furthermore, the intention to revisit and the inclination to recommend are key indicators of destination loyalty and sustainability. Consequently, this study identifies that tourists are not only willing to recommend the Ada region as an admirable vacation destination for families and friends (mean = 3.98), but their experiences have also created a positive image of Ada as a go-to emerging destination (mean = 3.91) (Table 6). This can foster a delightful and positive foundation for repeated visitation and destination endorsement (Buhalis & Foerste, 2015). Recognizing that the intention to revisit and the willingness to recommend are crucial markers of destination loyalty and sustainability, stakeholders in the Ada region can leverage such positive perceptions (Chen et al., 2020). Efforts should therefore be directed towards enhancing and promoting the region's positive image and fostering delightful experiences. Thus, the destination can attract a higher volume of repeat visitors and benefit from positive word-of-mouth recommendations, contributing to long-term tourism success and economic growth.

5. Conclusion

5.1 Discussion

This study delves into the influential factors shaping tourists' decisions to revisit and recommend the emerging Ada tourist destination in Ghana. The empirical findings shed light on the pivotal elements that influence tourists' intentions to revisit and recommend the Ada destination. This establishes a foundation for comprehending destination attributes that contribute to tourist satisfaction and value for money. The study underlined the factors that characterize Ada region as an emerging tourist destination, and this included "climate and natural attraction," "destination image," "accessibility and infrastructure suitability," "entertainment and comfort," and "hospitality and cultural appeal." Among these, "climate and natural attraction" emerged as the foremost factor driving repeat visits and recommendations for the emerging Ada destination. This signifies Ada's appeal, offering fresh water for tourism, pleasant weather, diverse natural resources, unique islands, and pristine beaches. Consequently, sustaining and enhancing Ada's natural and clean attributes, coupled with improved water cruising experiences, are imperative for fostering repeat visits and positive destination recommendations. The destination's wealth of natural resources, adventure, beautiful islands, and beaches positions it as a destination for enjoyment, recreation, and relaxation. Overall, the findings point to a strategic focus for destination managers, emphasizing the preservation of natural qualities and elevating water-related experiences to solidify the destination's position as a sought-after destination for recreation and relaxation (Lee & Hsu 2013; Wang & Li 2019; Zhang et al. 2014).

In assessing the perceived value influencing tourists' decisions to revisit and recommend Ada as an emerging destination, two significant factors emerged: 'value with individual attributes' and 'value with overall attributes' of the destination. While tourists' perceived

value for money in the overall destination attributes, this sentiment was limited to the entertainment aspect of the Ada region when considering ‘individual attributes.’ Notably, the mean scores in Table 4 reveal that tourists did not find value for money in accommodation, food services, transportation, or attraction fees. This suggests a critical need for destination stakeholders to strategically enhance these specific areas, aligning them with tourists’ value expectations to fortify the overall appeal of Ada, offer value for money, and inspire repeat visits and positive recommendations (Kim et al., 2015).

The results also indicate that tourists visiting the Ada destination region are highly satisfied with the beaches, internet connectivity, safety, and security levels within the destination, islands, and entertainment/nightlife. These factors significantly influenced the intention to make repeat visits and recommendations. This resonates with studies highlighting the significance of attractions and well-maintained infrastructure in visitor satisfaction with tourist destination revisit and recommendations (Buhalis & Michopoulou, 2011). However, the road network, transportation system/services, and monuments/museums did not meet the tourists’ satisfaction levels. This echoes prior research on the critical importance of efficient transportation and cultural offerings in shaping tourists’ perceptions and revisits intentions (Li & Wang, 2021; Gursoy et al., 2016). These aspects represent notable challenges that require attention to enhance a destination's accessibility and overall appeal. Addressing these challenges is crucial for destination managers to enhance accessibility and overall appeal, aligning with the interconnected dynamics of satisfaction, recommendations, and revisiting intentions highlighted in the literature (Choi & Chu, 2018; Li et al., 2018). Strategic interventions in these areas are essential to ensure a well-rounded and satisfying tourist experience, aligning to foster destination loyalty and positive recommendations among visitors. This study reveals tourists’ intentions to revisit and recommend the emerging Ada destination as a future vacation spot. The results align with previous research to emphasize that tourist’ experiences and satisfaction with service products and destination attributes contribute to repeat visit intentions and destination recommendations (Chi & Qu, 2008). Therefore, destination managers should prioritize attributes that position Ada as a repeat tourism destination and work to enhance less-performing attributes to obtain tourist loyalty and gain competitive advantages.

5.2 Implications

In conclusion, this research provides valuable insights into the influential factors guiding tourists’ decisions to revisit and recommend emerging Ada tourist destinations in Ghana. By highlighting key elements, such as climate, natural attractions, and overall destination image, this study establishes a foundation for understanding tourist satisfaction and value for money across these destination attributes. The significance of "climate and natural attraction” emerges prominently, underlining Ada’s appeal for freshwater, pleasant weather, diverse natural resources, unique islands, and primeval beaches.

To solidify Ada’s position as a truly desirous emerging destination and move it to a desired fully-fledged destination, sustaining and enhancing its natural attributes, eco-based tours coupled with improved water cruising experiences, is imperative. More importantly, local government and destination management teams must micromanage the destination to ensure that all elements of the destination, lodging, dining, attractions, and transportation meet certain standards of quality and fairness in terms of the value they offer to visitors. The goal is to ensure that these facilities and services provide fair value for the money visitors spend. The study further emphasizes a strategic focus on preserving natural qualities and elevating water-related experiences to continuously reinforce Ada as a sought-after destination for nature, fresh water, and coastal recreation and relaxation spots.

Likewise, the study highlights tourists’ satisfaction with aspects such as internet connectivity, safety, island tourism, and entertainment while expressing challenges with the road network, transportation, and historical monuments/museums. Addressing challenges in

road networks, transportation, and cultural offerings is central to aligning the interconnected dynamics of satisfaction, recommendations, and repeat intentions. Future interventions should prioritize enhancing the less-performing attributes and areas where value for money was not achieved, as explored in this study. This priority approach can foster a strong destination identity, competitive advantages, and loyalty, continually placing the Ada destination in the minds and intents of all travellers, to make them conscious ambassadors of the destination and region.

5.3 Limitations

This study had some limitations. First, it focuses on both international and domestic tourists, and future research should separately investigate these groups to identify the specific factors that uniquely influence their revisit intentions and destination recommendations. This research also concentrated solely on the emerging Ada destination in Ghana, limiting the generalizability of the findings to broader tourist contexts. Different destinations may have distinct influencing factors, and this study's insights may not be universally applicable to diverse tourism settings. Future research should consider multiple destinations to capture a more comprehensive understanding of tourists' revisit intentions and recommendations.

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